

Mistletoe Germination - Raw Data Biomechanical Analysis- Teixeira-Costa, Wiese, Speck & Mylo

Biomechanical analysis - seed samples

Sample-ID	Harvest-Date	Diameter 1	Diameter 2	Surface Area	Maximum Force	Elongation at break	Maximum Strength	Failure type
		[mm]	[mm]	[mm ²]	[N]	[mm]	[N/mm ²]	
A-s-02	23.06.2023	4.39	2.73	9.4	8.43	0.32	0.90	partially torn
A-s-03	23.06.2023	4.22	3.02	10.0	2.74	0.28	0.27	partially torn
A-s-04	23.06.2023	4.61	3.34	12.1	4.30	0.21	0.36	partially torn
A-s-06	23.06.2023	4.90	3.26	12.5	3.27	0.09	0.26	partially torn
A-s-07	23.06.2023	3.66	3.00	8.6	4.47	0.12	0.52	partially torn
A-s-08	25.07.2023	2.50	4.64	9.1	6.40	0.09	0.70	partially torn
A-s-09	25.07.2023	2.03	4.36	7.0	3.95	0.10	0.57	partially torn
A-s-11	25.07.2023	2.79	3.15	6.9	3.82	0.15	0.55	completely detached
A-s-13	25.07.2023	2.72	4.94	10.6	4.39	0.13	0.42	partially torn
A-s-15	25.07.2023	2.27	3.85	6.9	2.27	0.09	0.33	partially torn
A-s-16	25.07.2023	2.38	4.35	8.1	1.87	0.15	0.23	only tissue
A-s-18	25.07.2023	3.97	3.02	9.4	2.95	0.08	0.31	partially torn
A-s-19	25.07.2023	3.86	2.59	7.9	2.73	0.12	0.35	partially torn
A-s-20	10.08.2023	2.87	4.20	9.5	4.28	0.09	0.45	partially torn
A-s-21	10.08.2023	2.45	3.67	7.1	3.87	0.18	0.55	partially torn
A-s-22	10.08.2023	2.57	3.95	8.0	3.46	0.23	0.43	partially torn
A-s-24	11.08.2023	2.78	3.77	8.2	2.39	0.11	0.29	partially torn
A-s-25	11.08.2023	2.50	3.30	6.5	2.92	0.09	0.45	partially torn
A-s-26	11.08.2023	1.77	3.02	4.2	1.24	0.37	0.30	partially torn
A-s-27	11.08.2023	3.95	2.22	6.9	0.72	0.12	0.10	partially torn
A-s-28	11.08.2023	3.00	3.73	8.8	1.70	0.39	0.19	partially torn
A-s-29	11.08.2023	2.03	2.69	4.3	0.79	0.35	0.18	partially torn
A-s-30	11.08.2023	2.70	2.83	6.0	2.60	0.11	0.43	completely detached
A-s-32	11.08.2023	2.74	2.84	6.1	2.74	0.34	0.45	partially torn
A-s-33	11.08.2023	1.65	2.37	3.1	2.13	0.09	0.69	partially torn
A-s-34	11.08.2023	4.84	4.42	16.8	2.60	0.11	0.15	partially torn
A-s-35	11.08.2023	2.95	3.42	7.9	2.31	0.14	0.29	partially torn
A-s-36	11.08.2023	2.53	4.24	8.4	3.95	0.17	0.47	partially torn
A-s-40	11.08.2023	2.27	3.65	6.5	1.86	0.11	0.29	completely detached
A-s-41	11.08.2023	2.94	3.14	7.3	4.42	0.10	0.61	partially torn
A-s-42	11.08.2023	2.11	3.76	6.2	1.47	0.09	0.24	completely detached
A-s-43	11.08.2023	2.74	2.21	4.8	2.36	0.19	0.50	partially torn
A-s-44	11.08.2023	4.18	1.83	6.0	2.29	0.09	0.38	partially torn
A-s-45	11.08.2023	2.24	3.08	5.4	1.29	0.10	0.24	completely detached
A-s-46	11.08.2023	3.14	3.10	7.6	3.45	0.15	0.45	partially torn
A-s-47	11.08.2023	4.11	2.52	8.1	1.52	0.02	0.19	partially torn

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Biomechanical analysis - holdfast samples

Sample-ID	Harvest-Date	Diameter 1	Diameter 2	Surface Area	Maximum Force	Elongation at break	Maximum Strength	Failure type
		[mm]	[mm]	[mm ²]	[N]	[mm]	[N/mm ²]	
A-ho-01	23.06.2023	1.97	1.90	2.94	4.58	0.22	1.56	completely detached
A-ho-02	23.06.2023	2.22	2.54	4.43	3.30	0.41	0.75	completely detached
A-ho-03	23.06.2023	1.96	1.72	2.65	2.33	0.33	0.88	completely detached
A-ho-04	25.07.2023	1.37	1.63	1.75	5.37	0.17	3.06	completely detached
A-ho-05	25.07.2023	1.67	2.39	3.13	2.36	0.24	0.75	partially torn
A-ho-06	25.07.2023	2.22	2.39	4.17	2.70	0.05	0.65	partially torn
A-ho-07	25.07.2023	1.52	1.73	2.07	2.48	0.24	1.20	completely detached
A-ho-09	25.07.2023	1.43	1.48	1.66	1.94	0.38	1.16	completely detached
A-ho-10	25.07.2023	1.75	1.47	2.02	3.00	0.22	1.49	completely detached
A-ho-11	25.07.2023	2.05	2.17	3.49	2.87	0.14	0.82	completely detached
A-ho-12	25.07.2023	1.53	1.59	1.91	3.44	0.18	1.80	completely detached
A-ho-13	25.07.2023	1.55	2.09	2.54	2.45	0.27	0.96	completely detached
A-ho-14	10.08.2023	2.10	1.90	3.13	1.67	0.07	0.53	completely detached
A-ho-15	10.08.2023	1.84	1.76	2.54	2.69	0.20	1.06	partially torn
A-ho-16	11.08.2023	1.82	1.38	1.97	2.79	0.19	1.42	completely detached
A-ho-18	11.08.2023	1.46	1.78	2.04	1.87	0.06	0.92	completely detached
A-ho-22	11.08.2023	1.55	1.70	2.07	2.31	0.08	1.12	completely detached
A-ho-23	11.08.2023	1.85	1.85	2.69	3.33	0.09	1.24	completely detached
A-ho-24	11.08.2023	1.47	1.40	1.62	3.88	0.16	2.40	completely detached
A-ho-25 (1)	11.08.2023	1.68	1.91	2.52	2.52	0.22	1.00	completely detached
A-ho-26 (2)	11.08.2023	1.79	1.96	2.76	6.24	0.18	2.27	completely detached
A-ho-27	11.08.2023	1.80	1.83	2.59	2.66	0.18	1.03	completely detached
A-ho-28	11.08.2023	1.13	1.41	1.25	2.56	0.08	2.05	completely detached
A-ho-29	29.11.2023	2.25	2.36	4.17	11.05	0.26	2.65	completely detached

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Biomechanical analysis - holdfast samples

Sample-ID	Harvest-Date	Maximum Force	Results
		[N]	
A-hy-01	23.06.2023	2.07	Holdfast-detachment
A-hy-02	25.07.2023	2.32	Holdfast-detachment
A-hy-03	25.07.2023	1.88	Holdfast-detachment
A-hy-04	25.07.2023	5.82	Hypocotyl-rupture at the side of the seed
A-hy-05	25.07.2023	3.14	Hypocotyl-rupture at the side of the seed
A-hy-06	25.07.2023	1.94	Holdfast-detachment
A-hy-07	25.07.2023	2.73	Hypocotyl-rupture at the side of the seed
A-hy-08	10.08.2023	3.38	Hypocotyl-rupture at the side of the holdfast
A-hy-09	10.08.2023	1.81	Seed-detachment
A-hy-10	10.08.2023	1.94	Holdfast-detachment
A-hy-11	11.08.2023	3.51	Hypocotyl-rupture at the side of the seed
A-hy-12	11.08.2023	0.92	Seed-detachment
A-hy-13	11.08.2023	2.17	Holdfast-detachment
A-hy-14	15.11.2023	3.13	Hypocotyl-rupture at the side of the seed
A-hy-15	22.11.2023	1.49	Seed-detachment
A-hy-16	29.11.2023	0.95	Hypocotyl-rupture at the side of the seed
A-hy-17	29.11.2023	1.33	Seed-detachment